

The Starfish: a Giant Step Toward Origins of Life

"If I followed correctly, the circular RNA sequence obeys the Fibonacci rule. If we extrapolate, we can think that Life was formed (or was created, according to our religion) from this RNA according to a mathematical principle? "

(Luc Montagnier)

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ABSTRACT :

Here we study the circular RNA sequence of 22 bases named ALpha, which is supposed to be a candidate for the emergence of life on earth. We demonstrate how this sequence is structured by Fibonacci proportions, then we demonstrate that, among the millions of known sequences, it is in the starfish genome that we find this sequence with the highest homology, thus uniting the scales of RNA and morphogenesis since the geometry of the starfish is also structured by the Golden Ratio.

-I- the Starfish:

The Starfish has always fascinated people because of its great aesthetics. Beauty inherited from its geometric link with the 5-pointed star and the pentagon in which the ratio of the diagonal to the side is the famous Golden Ratio $\Phi = 1.618033$. (Perez JC. Codon populations in single-stranded whole human genome DNA Are fractal and fine-tuned by the Golden Ratio 1.618. Interdiscip Sci. 2010 Sep;2(3):228-40. doi: 10.1007/s12539-010-0022-0. Epub 2010 Jul 25. Erratum in: Interdiscip Sci. 2010 Dec;2(4):373. PMID: 20658335 <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/20658335/>). Which corresponds for the starfish to the ratio of the distances between (one branch and the next of its neighbor) and (one branch and its neighbor). Or if we number the branches from 1 to 5, (distance 1 and 3) / distance 1 and 2). It was not until 2023 that the entire genome of the beautiful and intriguing STARFISH was sequenced ([https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nucleotide/OX465102.1?report=genbank&log\\$=nuclalign&blast_rank=1&RID=XN5H46XM016](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nucleotide/OX465102.1?report=genbank&log$=nuclalign&blast_rank=1&RID=XN5H46XM016)).It is

this recent discovery of the genomic sequence of the starfish which will provide new insight into the scientific quest for the origins of terrestrial life...

The Starfish

-II- Is there an original RNA?

When Golden Ratio emerges from Fractal Chaos

As in the fractal universe, where everything is self-similar at all scales, let us now travel towards the infinitely small universe of RNA which is said to be at the origins of life on earth or rather in the seas. .. Like the star of the sea... From 2007 in A possible circular RNA at the origin of life (Demongeot, J. (2007). A possible circular RNA at the origin of life. Journal of Theoretical Biology.

https://www.academia.edu/76445494/A_possible_circular_RNA_at_the_origin_of_life?email_work_card=title

Demongeot and Moreira, Then In (Demongeot, J.; Norris, V. Emergence of a "Cyclosome" in a Primitive Network Capable of Building "Infinite" Proteins. Life 2019, 9, 51. <https://doi.org/10.3390/life9020051>), Demongeot and Norris argue for the existence of an RNA sequence, called the AL (for ALpha) sequence, which may have played a role at the origin of life;

Here is this "ring" sequence that they called "ALpha":

AUGGUACUGCCA UUCAAGAUGA

-III- Fibonacci proportions structure the original Alpha RNA sequence:

In (Perez, J.C. (2021). SARS-COV2 VARIANTS AND VACCINES MRNA SPIKES FIBONACCI NUMERICAL UA/CG METASTRUCTURES. International Journal of Research -GRANTHAALAYAH, 9(6), 349-396. <https://doi.org/10.29121/granthaalayah.v9.i6.2021.4040>) with RIP Luc Montagnier, we demonstrated how this strange circular RNA "ALpha ring" sequence, 22 nucleotides long (AUGGUACUGCCA UUCAAGAUGA) obeyed the Fibonacci proportions for the UA/CG populations throughout the ALpha circular ring.

We also note $2 \times 6 = 12$ bases in primers of palindromes or mirror series:

AUGGUA mirror and UCAAGA quasi palindrome.

Let's organize this circular sequence into codon triplets and gradually shift it codon triplet by codon triplet.

```
=> Aug GUA CUG CCA UUC AAG AUG A 13AU & 8CG
Au GGU ACU GCC AUU CAA G => Aug A 13AU & 8CG
Au GGU ACU GCC AUU C => AAG Aug A 13AU & 8CG
Au GGU ACU GCC A => UUC AAG Aug A 13AU & 8CG
Au GGU ACU G => CCA UUC AAG Aug A 13AU & 8CG
Au GGU A => CUG CCA UUC AAG Aug A 13AU & 8CG
Au G => GUA CUG CCA UUC AAG Aug A 13AU & 8CG
```

This sequence is entirely structured by proportions of nucleotides obeying the proportions of the Fibonacci sequences (13AU and 8CG). Let's drag this sequence gradually one nucleotide at a time:

AUGGUACUGCCA UUCAAGAUGA

```
AUGGUACUGCCA UUCAAGAUGA
AAUGGUACUGCCA UUCAAGAUG
GAAUGGUACUGCCA UUCAAGAU
UGAAUGGUACUGCCA UUCAAGA
AUGAAUGGUACUGCCA UUCAAG
GAUGAAUGGUACUGCCA UUCA
... /...
```

```
GAUGAAUGGUA CUGCCA UUCA
```

```
GAUGAAUGGUA
AACUUACCGUC
```

Weak matches (UA. vs. CG)

GAUGAAUGGUA
!!!!!!!!!!!!
AACUUACCGUC

Strong matches.

GAUGAAUGGUA
!!!!!!!!!!
AACUUACCGUC

So this circular RNA can fold into a sort of “hairpin”.

We then see that, less constrained than a Formal correspondence, CG or UA, the more flexible form of UA/CG correspondences allowed by the Fibonacci proportions also constitutes a way of locating palindromes.

There is therefore a certain potential for PALINDROME

There is therefore a certain potential for PALINDROME type symmetry where circular RNA when folding highlights UA and CG base pairs, as in DNA.

Particularly, this hyper constrained circular 22nt sequence codes for the twenty amino acids + codon stop + only one redundant amino acid (MET).

Seen from the point of view of the autopoiesis Francisco Varela theory (ref Varela), autonomy of Indoor vs. Outdoor systems, these results could be interpreted as the rest of the loop of 21 UACG (outdoor) "seen" from a base C or G (indoor). So, the perceived signal is a kind of Fibonacci resonance ... By virtue of Francisco Varela's theory of autopoiesis (Varela & Maturana, 1980) that we applied to Artificial Intelligence in the 1980s by creating the “fractal chaos” artificial neural network (Perez 1988). Thus, the Fibonacci numbers, therefore the optimal proportion of the Golden Ratio would perhaps have already been present from the first moments of life on earth, a life for which they would have served as a "matrix" ...

-IV- Among the millions of sequences and genomes sequenced, which one is closest to ALpha RNA?

We searched using BLASTn for the closest homologies to this famous original ALpha candidate sequence.

Here are the 3 closest sequences:

The 3 sequences closest to the original RNA

AUGGUACUGCCAUAUCAAGAUGA

Homologies in descending order:

1/ ==> Starfish 21/22

The Starfish

2/ ==> *Protonemura montana* insect 20/22

***Protonemura montana* insect**

3/ ==> *Armillaria ostoyae* mushroom 19/22

***Armillaria ostoyae* mushroom**

Details:

Luidia sarsii genome assembly, chromosome: 2

Sequence ID: [OX465102.1](#) Length: 31917233 Number of Matches: 1

Range 1: 25087392 to 25087412 [GenBankGraphics](#) [Next Match](#) [Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Gaps	Strand
42.1 bits(21)	0.65	21/21(100%)	0/21(0%)	Plus/Minus
Query 1		ATGGTACTGCCATTCAAGATG	21	
Sbjct 25087412		ATGGTACTGCCATTCAAGATG	25087392	

[Download](#) [GenBankGraphics](#) [Next](#) [Previous](#) [Descriptions](#)

Protonemura montana genome assembly, chromosome: 9

Sequence ID: [OX387611.1](#) Length: 13083817 Number of Matches: 1

Range 1: 12093441 to 12093460 [GenBankGraphics](#) [Next Match](#) [Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Gaps	Strand
40.1 bits(20)	2.6	20/20(100%)	0/20(0%)	Plus/Plus
Query 2		TGGTACTGCCATTCAAGATG	21	
Sbjct 12093441		TGGTACTGCCATTCAAGATG	12093460	

[Download](#) [GenBankGraphics](#) [Next](#) [Previous](#) [Descriptions](#)

Armillaria ostoyae strain C18/9 genome assembly, chromosome: LG4

Sequence ID: [LR732078.1](#) Length: 5066647 Number of Matches: 1

Range 1: 1469717 to 1469735 [GenBankGraphics](#) [Next Match](#) [Previous Match](#)

Alignment statistics for match #1

Score	Expect	Identities	Gaps	Strand
38.2 bits(19)	10	19/19(100%)	0/19(0%)	Plus/Plus
Query 1		ATGGTACTGCCATTCAAGA	19	
Sbjct 1469717		ATGGTACTGCCATTCAAGA	1469735	

-V- Conclusion:

Three conclusions emerge from this interdisciplinary study: On the one hand, even if some doubt the reality of this hypothetical RNA ALpha sequence, it is remarkable that among the millions of genetic sequences available to date, it is, curiously, the starfish genome which is closest to this sequence.

On the other hand, the demonstration of structures linked to the golden ratio and its alter ego the Fibonacci sequence are common here, in a fractal and self-similar manner simultaneously at the 2 nanometric scales of its DNA and macroscopic of the form geometric of the starfish.

Finally, in

(<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/SIX-FRACTAL-CODES-OF-LIFE-FROM-BIOATOMS-ATOMIC-MASS-Perez-Montagnier/b332d3eed4a2f554c233da2e07ec68daab9a2182>)

we demonstrate (see figure) that, among the 3 biological universes DNA , RNA, proteins, the double strand of RNA, as we encounter in the transfer RNA of the universal genetic code, or here, in ALpha, Double stranded RNA constitutes a sort of zero or neutral element, unlike DNA and its proteomic images which are strongly correlated to it in what we call MASTER CODE of Biology (figure). This kind of zero could result physically, chemically and biologically in a great stability of these double-stranded RNAs for 2 reasons: this zero on the one hand, and the Fibonacci structures on the other hand.

Figure 4 A symbolic representation of the 3 worlds of double stranded DNA (Genomics) highly correlated with potential double stranded amino acids (Proteomics) while RNA double stranded

The RNA double strand constitutes a kind of ZERO of the Biology

The Master Code of Biology Unifying DNA and Proteomics Worlds

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